

REGULATION OF SPORTS UNDER INTERNATIONAL LAW: SPECIAL PRINCIPLES

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Abstract: A description of the principles of international legal regulation of sports is provided in this article.

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Jus cogens, or generally recognized principles of international law, have retained their significance in the implementation of international legal regulation in sports. In the UN Charter of June 26, 1945, seven principles are enshrined. In addition to sovereign equality, conscientious fulfillment of international obligations, peaceful resolution of international disputes, non-use of force or threat of force, cooperation, non-interference in internal affairs, and equality and self-determination for peoples are the principles of these principles. Furthermore, a number of special principles have emerged - guiding principles common to international law and *lex sportiva* that guide the regulation of international sports.

A fair play principle (Fair Play) is a principle of honor and nobility in sports as well as in life (1). The principle implies respect for the opponent, for the rules and decisions of the judges, as well as the athlete's self-control - the ability to control one's emotions and stoically accept any outcome of a competition. A narrow sense of the principle aims to combat doping in sports and violence in sports. This principle was enshrined in the IOC documents, as well as in a number of international legal acts - the UNESCO International Convention against Doping in Sport of October 19, 2005, the Council of Europe Anti-Doping Convention of November 16, 1989, and the Additional Protocol to it of September 12, 2002, as well as the European Convention on Violence and Misbehavior at Sports Events, namely Football Matches, of August 19, 1995.

The principle of preserving the environment during training and competition means that environmental requirements should be an important consideration when selecting cities to host the Olympic Games. The IOC Commission on Sport and the Environment has been in operation since 1994. In response to the UN Conference on Environment and Development in Rio de Janeiro in 1992, Agenda 21 was developed by the Olympic Movement on October 23, 1999. While some

scholars call this document the Ecological Charter of Olympic Sports, it is actually an example of "soft law" in the field of international regulation of sports. In order to combat discrimination in sports, all forms of discrimination - political, religious, racial - must be prohibited. It is enshrined in many international legal documents: in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of December 10, 1948, the UNESCO Declaration on Race and Racial Prejudice of November 27, 1978, the Declaration on the Elimination of All Forms of Intolerance and Discrimination Based on Religion or Belief of 25 November 1981, as well as in the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination of December 21, 1965, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of December 16, 1966, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of December 16, 1966 of the International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities of December 13, 2006. According to Article 1 of the 1973 Convention on the Suppression and Punishment of Apartheid.

The UN International Convention against Apartheid in Sports of December 10, 1985, added to the list. In the Convention, States Parties are required to impose sanctions on States that pursue apartheid policies. It was particularly important for the parties to the Convention to not maintain relations with state sports bodies, teams, and athletes, and also to prohibit athletes or teams participating in sports competitions in South Africa, which was under apartheid at the time of the Convention's adoption.

Olympic solidarity and internationalism are based on multilateral cooperation and the active involvement of developing countries. In sport, this principle also rejects the policy of colonialism and racial discrimination, which are closely related to the basic principle of international public law - the principle of equality and self-determination of people.

References:

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